

ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO`LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. KLASSIK GAUSS KVADRATURALARI.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10699876>

Gauss kvadraturalari matematika, fizika, injineriya va boshqa sohalarda juda muhim bo`lgan bir tushunchadir. Hisoblash matematikasi sohasida nazariy izlanishlar asosan, tipik matematik masalalarni yechishning sonli metodlar atrofida guruhlanadi. Bu sohaning klassik masalalaridan biri bu integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash formulalarini qurishdan iborat.

Bir karrali integrallarni son qiymatlari geometrik nuqtai nazardan qisqacha kvadratura deb ataladi.

Bunday masalalar bilan ko`pincha buyuk olimlar shug`ullanganlar. Masalan: Gauss, Chebishev, Eyler, Nyuton va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formular deganda quyidagi taqribiy tenglikni tushunamiz:

$$\int_B f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda} f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (1)$$

bu yerda C_{λ} - kvadratur formulaning koefitsientlari, $x^{(\lambda)}$ - tugun nuqtalari, N - tugun nuqtalar soni[2].

Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ uzluksiz funksiyani $[a,b]$ kesmada aniq integralni taqribiy hisoblovchi formulani qurish talab qilinsin.

Integralning eng sodda taqribiy ifodasi asosan $[a,b]$ kesma balandligi $f(x)$ ning $\frac{a+b}{2}$ nuqtadagi $f(\frac{a+b}{2})$ qiymatiga teng bo`lgan to`g`ri turtburchak yuzasining kattaligidan iborat.

Quyidagi kvadratur formulani hosil qilamiz.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx (b-a)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right), \quad (2)$$

Katta nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo`lgan kvadratur formulalar bilan bog`liq hisoblash algoritmlarini optimizizastiyalash masalalari bilan ko`pgina olimlar shug`ullanib kelgan[3-4]. Bulardan S.L.Sobolev, A.N.Kolmogorov, S.M.Nikolskiy va boshqalar.

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Klassik Gauss kvadraturalari uchun absissalar va vaznlar

Bu yerda biz ba`zi klassik Gauss integratsiya formulalarini sanab o`tamiz. $N = 1$ dan 5 gacha bo`lgan tugun absissalar va vaznlar jadvallari oltita kasrgacha yaxlitlangan.

Ushbu jadvallar qo`lda hisoblash uchun etarli bo`lishi kerak, ammo dasturlashda sizga aniqroq yoki ko`proq tugunlar kerak bo`lishi mumkin. Bunday holda siz integratsiya dasturidagi absissalar va vaznlarni hisoblash uchun boshqa manbalarga.³ murojaat qilishingiz yoki pastki dasturdan foydalanishingiz kerak.⁴

$$E = \int_a^b \omega(x)f(x)dx - \sum_{i=0}^n A_i f(x_i) \quad (1)$$

Gauss kvadraturasidagi kesish xatosi $E = K(n)f^{(2n+2)}(c)$, ko`rinishga ega, bu yerda $E = K(n)f^{(2n+2)}(c)$ (c ning qiymati noma`lum; faqat uning chegaralari berilgan). $K(n)$ ning ifodasi aniq kvadraturaga bog`liq. Agar $f(x)$ ning hosilalarini hisoblash mumkin bo`lsa, xato formulalari xato chegaralarini hisoblashda foydalidir.

Gauss - Lejandr kvadratur formulasi

$$\int_{-1}^1 f(\xi)d\xi \approx \sum_{i=0}^n A_i f(\xi_i) \quad (2)$$

Gauss - Legendre kvadraturasi eng ko`p ishlatiladigan Gauss integrallash formulasidir. 1-jadvaldan ko`rinib turibdiki, tugunlar taxminan $\xi = 0$ ga teng simmetrik tarzda joylashtirilgan va simmetrik juft tugunlar bilan bog`liq vaznlar tengdir. Masalan, $n=1$ uchun bizda $\xi_0 = -\xi_1$ va $A_0=A_1$ mavjud. (2) tenglamadagi kesish xatosi

$$E = \frac{2^{2n+3}[(n+1)!]^4}{(2n+3)[(2n+2)!]^3} f^{(2n+2)}(c), \quad -1 < c < 1 \quad (3)$$

ga teng.

$\pm \xi_i$	A_i	ξ_i	A_i
$n = 1$		$n = 4$	
0.577 350	1.000 000	0.000 000	0.568 889
$n = 2$		0.538 469	0.478 629
0.000 000	0.888 889	0.906 180	0.236 927

0.774 597	0.555 556			
$n = 3$			$n = 5$	
0.339 981	0.652 145		0.238 619	0.467 914
0.861 136	0.347 855		0.661 209	0.360 762
			0.932 470	0.171 324

1-jadval. Gauss -Legendre kvadraturasi uchun tugunlar va vaznlar.

Gauss -Legendre kvadraturasini $\int_a^b f(x)dx$ integraliga qo'llash uchun

avvalo (a,b) integratsiya diapazoni "standart" diapazonga $(-1,1)$ solishtirishimiz kerak. Biz buni o'zgartirish orqali amalga oshirishimiz mumkin.

$$x = \frac{b+a}{2} + \frac{b-a}{2} \xi \quad (4)$$

Endi $dx = d\xi(b-a)/2$ va kvadratura

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx \frac{b-a}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n A_i f(x_i) \quad (5)$$

ga o'zgaradi.

Bu yerda (4) tenglamadan x_i absissalarini hisoblash kerak. Bu erda kesish xatosi

$$E = \frac{(b-a)^{2n+3} [(n+1)!]^4}{(2n+3)[(2n+2)!]^3} f^{(2n+2)}(c), \quad a < c < b \quad (6)$$

Gauss - Chebishev kvadratur formulasi

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{-1/2} f(x)dx \approx \frac{\pi}{n+1} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i) \quad (7)$$

Barcha vaznlar tengdir: $A_i = \pi/(n+1)$, $x=0$ ga yaqin simmetrik bo'lgan tugunlarning absissalari bilan berilgan.

$$x_i = \cos \frac{(2i+1)\pi}{2n+2} \quad (8)$$

Kesish xatosi

$$E = \frac{2\pi}{2^{2n+2}(2n+2)!} f^{(2n+2)}(c), \quad -1 < c < 1 \quad (9)$$

Gauss - Lagger kvadratur formulasi

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx \frac{b-a}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n A_i f(x_i) \tag{10}$$

x_i	A_i	x_i	A_i
$n = 1$		$n = 4$	
0.585 786	0.853 554	0.263 560	0.521 756
3.414 214	0.146 447	1.413 403	0.398 667
		3.596 426	(-1)0.759 424
		7.085 810	(-2)0.361 175
		12.640 801	(-4)0.233 670
$n = 2$		$n = 5$	
0.415 775	0.711 093	0.538 469	0.478 629
34 280	0.278 517	0.906 180	0.236 927
6.289 945	(-1)0.103 892		
$n = 3$		$n = 5$	
0.322 548	0.603 154	0.222 847	0.458 964
1.745 761	0.357 418	1.188 932	0.417 000
		2.992 736	0.113 373
4.536 620	(-1)0.388 791	5.775 144	(-1)0.103 992
9.395 071	(-3)0.539 295	9.837 467	(-3)0.261 017
		15.982 874	(-6)0.898 548

2 -jadval. Gauss -Lager kvadraturasi uchun tugunlar va vaznlar (sonlarni 10^k ga ko`paytiriladi, bu erda k qavs ichida berilgan.)

$$E = \frac{[(n+1)!]^2}{(2n+2)!} f^{(2n+2)}(c), \quad 0 < c < \infty \tag{11}$$

Gauss - Ermit kvadratur formulasi

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} f(x)dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^n A_i f(x_i) \tag{12}$$

$\pm x_i$	A_i	$\pm x_i$	A_i
-----------	-------	-----------	-------

n	=	1	n	=	4				
0.707	107	0.886	227	0.000	000	0.945	308		
n	=	2	n	=	5				
0.000	000	1.181	636	2.020	183	(-1)	0.199	532	
1.224745	0.295	409	n	=	3				
n	=	3	0.436	077	0.724	629			
0.524	648	0.804	914	1.335	849	0.157	067		
1.650	680	(-1)	0.813	128	90	605	(-2)	0.453	001

3 -jadval. Gauss -Germit kvadraturasi uchun tugunlar va vaznlar (sonlarni 10^k ga ko'paytiriladi, bu erda k qavs ichida berilgan.)

Tugunlar nosimmetrik tarzda $x = 0$ ga yaqin joylashgan.

$$E = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(n+1)!}{2^2(2n+2)!} f^{(2n+2)}(c), \quad 0 < c < \infty \quad (13)$$

Logarifmik maxsuslikka ega Gauss kvadratur formulasi

$$\int_0^1 f(x) \ln x dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^n A_i f(x_i) \quad (14)$$

x_i	A_i	x_i	A_i
$n = 1$		$n = 4$	
0.112 009	0.718 539	(-1)0.291 345	0.297 893
0.602 277	0.281 461	0.173 977	0.349 776
$n = 2$		0.411 703	0.234 488
(-1)0.638 907	0.513 405	0.677314	(-1)0.989 305
0.368 997	0.391 980	0.894 771	(-1)0.189 116
0.766 880	(-1)0.946 154	$n = 5$	
$n = 3$		(-1)0.216 344	0.238 764
(-1)0.414 485	0.383 464	0.129 583	0.308 287
0.245 275	0.386 875	0.314 020	0.245 317
0.556 165	0.190 435	0.538 657	0.142 009
		0.756 916	(-1)0.554 546
		0.922 669	(-1)0.101690

4 -jadval. Logarifmik birlik bilan kvadratura uchun tugunlar va vaznlar (sonlarni 10^k ga ko`paytiriladi, bu erda k qavs ichida berilgan.)

$$E = \frac{k(n)}{(2n+1)!} f^{(2n+1)}(c), \quad 0 < c < 1 \quad (15)$$

Bunda $k(1)=0.00285$, $k(2)=0.00017$ va $k(3)=0.00001$.

Gauss tugunlari

Gauss funksiyasi "standart" interval $(-1,1)$ bo'yicha Gauss - Legendre kvadraturasida qo'llaniladigan tugun absissalari x_i va unga mos keladigan A_i vaznlarini hisoblaydi. Absissalarning taxminiy qiymatlari

$$x_i = \cos \frac{\pi(i + 0.75)}{m + 0.5} \quad (16)$$

ekanligini ko'rsatish mumkin. Bu yerda $m = n + 1$ tugunlar soni, integrallash tartibi deb ham ataladi. Ushbu yaqinlashishlarni boshlang'ich qiymatlar sifatida ishlatib, Nyuton usuli bilan Legendre polinomining $p_m(x)$ manfiy bo'lmagan nollarini topish yo'li bilan tugun absissalari hisoblanadi (salbiy nollar simmetriyadan olinadi). Agar e'tibor qaratadigan bo'lsak, gaussNodes subfunksiya legendreni chaqiradi, u $p_m(t)$ va uning hosilasini kortej (p,dp) sifatida qaytaradi.

modul gaussNodes

```
`` x,A = gaussNodes(m,tol=10e -9)
```

Gauss -Legendre m -nuqtali kvadraturasining

{x} tugun absissalari va vaznlari {A} ni aylantiradi.

```
````
```

```
import math
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
def gaussNodes(m,tol=10e -9):
```

```
 def legendre(t,m):
```

```
 p0 = 1.0; p1 = t
```

```
 for k in range(1,m):
```

```
 p = ((2.0*k + 1.0)*t*p1 - k*p0)/(1.0 + k)
```

```
 p0 = p1; p1 = p
```

```
 dp = m*(p0 - t*p1)/(1.0 - t**2)
```

```
 return p,dp
```

```
 A = np.zeros(m)
```

```
 x = np.zeros(m)
```

```
 nRoots = int((m + 1)/2) # Number of non -neg. roots
```

```

for i in range(nRoots):
 t = math.cos(math.pi*(i + 0.75)/(m + 0.5))# Approx. root
 for j in range(30):
 p,dp = legendre(t,m) # Newton -Raphson
 dt = -p/dp; t = t + dt # method
 if abs(dt) < tol:
 x[i] = t; x[m - i - 1] = -t
 A[i] = 2.0/(1.0 - t**2)/(dp**2) # (2.26) tenglama
 A[m - i - 1] = A[i]
 break
 return x, A

```

*GaussQuad funksiyasi m tugunlardan foydalangan holda GaussLegendre*

*kvadraturasi bilan  $\int_a^b f(x)dx$  ni hisoblash uchun gaussNodes -dan foydalanadi.*

*f(x) funksiyasi tartibi foydalanuvchi tomonidan taqdim etiladi.*

*## module gaussQuad*

*`` I = gaussQuad(f,a,b,m).*

*def legendre(t,m):*

*p0 = 1.0; p1 = t*

*for k in range(1,m):*

*p = ((2.0\*k + 1.0)\*t\*p1 - k\*p0)/(1.0 + k)*

*p0 = p1; p1 = p*

*dp = m\*(p0 - t\*p1)/(1.0 - t\*\*2)*

*return p,dp*

*A = np.zeros(m)*

*x = np.zeros(m)*

*nRoots = int((m + 1)/2) # Number of non -neg. roots*

*for i in range(nRoots):*

*t = math.cos(math.pi\*(i + 0.75)/(m + 0.5))# Approx. root*

*for j in range(30):*

*p,dp = legendre(t,m) # Newton -Raphson*

*dt = -p/dp; t = t + dt # method*

*if abs(dt) < tol:*

*x[i] = t; x[m - i - 1] = -t*

*A[i] = 2.0/(1.0 - t\*\*2)/(dp\*\*2) # Eq.(2.26)*



$$A[m - i - 1] = A[i]$$

*break*

*return x,A*

*GaussQuad funksiyasi m tugunlar yordamida GaussLegendre kvadraturasi*

*bilan  $\int_a^b f(x)dx$  ni hisoblash uchun gaussNodesdan foydalanadi.  $f(x)$  funksiyasi*

*tartibi foydalanuvchi tomonidan taqdim etiladi.*

## module gaussQuad

`` I = gaussQuad(f,a,b,m).

f(x) ning x = a dan b gacha bo`lgan integralini

Gauss -Legendre kvadraturasi bilan m tugun yordamida hisoblaydi.

``

from gaussNodes import \*

def gaussQuad(f,a,b,m):

c1 = (b + a)/2.0

c2 = (b - a)/2.0

x,A = gaussNodes(m)

sum = 0.0

for i in range(len(x)):

sum = sum + A[i]\*f(c1 + c2\*x[i])

return c2\*sum

## MISOL VA DASTUR

### 1. Misol

Gauss integrallashi bilan  $\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{3/2} f(x)dx$  ni hisoblaymiz.

**Masalaning yechimi.** Integral silliq va birliksiz bo`lgani uchun biz Gauss - Legendre kvadraturasidan foydalanishimiz mumkin. Biroq, aniq integralni Gauss -Chebishev formulasi bilan olish mumkin. Biz

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{3/2} f(x)dx = \int_{-1}^1 \frac{(1-x^2)^2}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx$$

ni yozamiz.



$f(x) = (1 - x^2)^2$  numeratori to'rtinchi darajali ko'phad bo'lgani uchun Gauss Chebyshev kvadraturasi uchta tugun bilan aniq bo'ladi.

Tugunlarning absissalari (8) tenglamadan olinadi.  $n = 2$  ni almashtirsak,

$$x_i = \cos \frac{\pi(2i+1)}{6}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2$$

ni olamiz.

Demak,

$$x_0 = \cos \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$x_1 = \cos \frac{\pi}{2} = 0$$

$$x_2 = \cos \frac{5\pi}{6} = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

Qiymatlar topiladi va (7) tenglama

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1 - x^2)^{3/2} f(x) dx \approx \frac{\pi}{3} \sum_{i=0}^2 (1 - x_i^2)^2 = \frac{\pi}{3} \left[ \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right)^2 + (1 - 0)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right)^2 \right] = \frac{3\pi}{8}$$

ni hosil qiladi.

### Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

1. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
2. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 14(14).
3. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
4. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.
5. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
6. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.



7. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
8. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
9. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
10. Quvvatov, B. (2024). DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMALAR VA AMALIY ECHIMLAR ORQALI MAXSUS MODELLARNI QURISH. Menejment va iqtisodiyotda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish , 3 (1), 108-115.
11. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali , 3 (5), 269-273.
12. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DINAMIK HAMKORLIK. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali , 10 (11).
13. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. GAUSS KVADRATUR FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 114-125.
14. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. ORTOGONAL KOPHADLAR. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(2), 47-59.
15. Quvvatov, B. (2024, February). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. REKURSIV TRAPETSIYALAR QOIDASI. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 41-51).

